

ized knapsack mistblower. We used a D-vac suction sampler to assess insect populations in 8 m² of each plot.

BPH populations in plots sprayed with methyl parathion and decamethrin were higher than in control plots. Plots

treated with monocrotophos yielded the most, followed by plots with al-phacypermethrin + BPMC (see table). Plots treated with cypermethrin and decamethrin yielded less than the control plots.

The results imply that methyl parathion and decamethrin could induce high BPH densities. Treated fields did not yield higher than the control, which suggests that insecticide applications might not benefit yields. □

Hourly catches of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB moth catches were recorded from 6 p.m. to 6 a.m. at the Rice Research Station, Tirur, for a 24-d period coinciding with peak brood emergence. Three traps—a local bamboo light trap with 40 W incandescent bulb, and modified Robinson light traps with 125 W mercury vapor lamp and 200 W incandescent bulb—were located 100 m apart. Moth catches were transferred to separate containers at hourly intervals, separated by sex, counted, and a cumulative percentage worked out (see figure).

Cumulative percentage of YSB catch in light traps at hourly intervals from 6 p.m. to 6 a.m.

Peak moth catch occurred at 9 to 10 p.m. Sixty-four percent of the females and 62% of the males were caught before

midnight. There was a slight spurt in moth activity from 1 to 4 a.m. for females and from 4 to 5 a.m. for males. □

Effect of rice stage and GLH density on pipunculid parasitism on green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* in Bali, Indonesia

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Pipunculid flies are natural enemies of GLH, a vector of rice tungro, but their activities in the tropics are not well known. Observations in major rice-producing areas of Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Bali, and Lombok from 1986 to 1990 showed cases in which pipunculid parasitism rate was more than 80%.

We surveyed 83 ricefields in asynchronously planted areas in Bali for this

Pipunculid parasitism on *N. virescens* in 1989 dry season and 1989/90 wet season.^a

Rice crop age	Dry season			Wet season		
	GLH caught (no.)	GLH parasitized (%)	MF (%)	GLH caught (no.)	GLH parasitized (%)	MF (%)
Nursery beds	63	6.3	43.6	84	7.1	62.0
3-4 WT	76	14.5	41.4	186	14.5	56.6
5-6 WT	151	10.6	21.1	738	21.8	16.0
7-8 WT	200	23.5	1.4	148	29.1	5.5
9-10 WT	-	-	-	203	26.1	8.6
Ratoon	105	6.7	47.8	64	28.1	14.3

^aWT = weeks after transplanting. MF = proportion of mature females among parasite-free females.

study. GLH adults were collected by net sweeps in 1989 dry season and 1989/90 wet season. Insects were dissected under a binocular microscope to observe for pipunculid larvae and for the proportion of mature females among parasite-free females.

Relation of pipunculid parasitism rate to GLH adult density in ricefields 5-8 WT. Regression line is $Y = 17.5 + 10.5X$, $r = 0.49$ (<0.01), where Y is are sin-transformed.

Parasitism was lowest in nursery beds in all seasons (see table). Because immigrants were most common in young fields, these results suggest that parasitized GLH may be less migratory than parasite-free GLH. Parasitism in ratoon

fields markedly differed between the two seasons. This may be associated with the high percentage of mature females.

Fields 5-8 wk after transplanting are commonly major sources of GLH migrants in asynchronous areas. Using

pooled data, parasitism at this rice stage was positively correlated with GLH density (see figure). This suggests pipunculid parasites may be a regulatory factor in GLH abundance. □

Evaluating high temperature tolerance in the brown planthopper (BPH)

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An increasing body of knowledge suggests that rising concentrations of CO₂ and other gases will raise the earth's temperature substantially. Some scientists have estimated possible increases of 3 ± 1.5°C to even 8-10°C within the next 40 yr. The ways in which rice pest species might respond to this change depend on factors including direct effects on survival; physiological tolerance and interspecific interactions, such as competition, predation, and parasitization; and changes in habitat suitability. A species' ability to adapt to global warming and colonize new areas depends on its ecological versatility and tolerance for temperature extremes.

We used a direct assay method to evaluate high temperature tolerance of BPH populations. Ten 1-d-old individuals from respective populations and stages were caged in a cylindrical (54 × 5.5 cm diam) mylar cage with a 60-d-old rice plant trimmed to a single tiller. We placed 35 replications of this setup in a growth chamber at 40°C with 12:12 h illumination and 70% relative humidity. (Earlier work had shown that mortality increased sharply at 40°C.) At 5-h intervals, we removed five randomly selected cages from the chamber and recorded insect mortality. A similar setup at room temperature was used as the control.

The close was the time that the insects were exposed to high temperature to produce mortality. Thus, the dose (hours of exposure to 40°C) is the variable and the number of dead insects, the quantal response. We subjected the data to probit analysis using Abbott's formula to adjust for mortality in the control cages. The median effective doses (LT₅₀ expressed in days) were estimated.

Macropterous females were most tolerant of high temperatures (see figure). The relative potency compared with that of the brachypterous females was estimated to be 2.53 ± 0.32 (at 95% confidence limit). Tolerance of the nymphal stages was also higher than that of the brachypterous females. BPH populations maintained on rice cultivars TN1, Mudgo, and ASD7 did

not significantly differ in tolerance (see table).

High temperature tolerance in the macropterous BPH females is a clear advantage for range shifts. This intrinsic colonization ability, along with the species' high fecundity, implies that BPH is extremely adaptable to global warming conditions. □

Median effective doses (LT₅₀) of 1-d-old brachypterous BPH females reared on 3 rice cultivars.

Stage	Cultivar	LT ₅₀	Fiducial limits	Slope
1st instar	TN1	23.4	18.3 - 35.4	5.0
	Mudgo	24.6	18.3 - 36.6	4.7
	ASD7	27.1	24.8 - 30.2	4.2
3d instar	TN1	22.8	16.6 - 37.1	2.6
	Mudgo	24.1	18.1 - 38.3	2.4
	ASD7	24.6	16.6 - 50.8	2.0
5th instar	TN1	27.3	25.2 - 30.2	4.6
	Mudgo	32.2	29.4 - 38.7	4.8
	ASD7	34.2	30.8 - 40.6	4.2
Brachypterous females	TN1	16.9	14.8 - 17.1	5.6
	Mudgo	13.2	9.2 - 16.5	5.2
	ASD7	14.8	12.1 - 17.2	7.0

Probit lines of 1-d-old female BPH from different rice cultivars exposed to 40°C.